

FLAT SUN IN HEAT SUPPLY SYSTEMS OF COLLECTORS WORKING PARAMETERS

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Abstract : Heat in this article supply in systems flat the sun of collectors work parameters today state level current from issues one is considered especially this problems solution in reaching their optimization separately importance occupation it is said that

Key words: heat supply, flat sun collectors, solar from energy, solar heat supply with artificial pump circulation, renewable energy, in Heat supply systems

Sun in the world one of the most priority areas of practical use of energy - sunny heat supply systems. Developed countries, including the US, China, India, Japan, Germany, Sweden and Russia like in the states, the sun from energy use in the field scientific In researches, it has high economic efficiency, cheap and simple solar collectors and systems create, their price and of them use in time spend expenses decrease issues leader is taking place . In this regard, flat solar in heat supply systems of collectors work parameters optimization through their efficiency increase important importance occupation is enough.

of the world leader scientific in the centers sunny heat supply systems to improve in particular flat the sun of collectors work parameters optimization through their effective gini increase new methods to create directed scientific studies take is going This in the direction one and two contoured, natural

thermosiphon and artificial pump circulation solar heat supply systems heat in the solar contour carrier small with spending performance and demand done up to temperature one times heating up at the expense of the most solar collectors by providing an optimal mode effective Research on the modeling of growth processes is a priority is being counted. At the same time, in solar heat supply systems the sun radiation stationary didn't happen come drop off in the circumstances natural thermosyphon circulation model and solar collectors heat work release productivity to determine method improve- strain as one of the urgent tasks is being counted.

Wide benefits of renewable energy sources in our republic contact and efficiency to increase help giving new technology on conducting research on the creation of s and their practical application wide scope measures done is increasing. 2022-2026 for years intended New of Uzbekistan development in strategy, including "Uninterrupted supply of electricity to the economy" and "Green active introduction of "economy" technologies to all sectors, economy increase the energy efficiency of the yacht by 20 percent" ¹ duties on defined. This tasks done in raising in particular again erect building new production capacities based on renewable energy sources Rish and modernization of existing ones, including heat supply optimization of the operating parameters of flat solar collectors in systems to make through their efficiency increase important is considered

Optimization of parameters of operation of flat solar collectors in heat supply systems through their efficiency to increase directed studies of the world leader higher education institutions and scientific in the centers in particular University of

Wisconsin–Madison (USA), Shanghai Jiao Morning University (China people Republic), Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (India), Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee (India), National Institute of Technology Hamirpur (India), Tamkang University (Taiwan), University of Tanta (Egypt), University Nationality Malaysia (Malaysia), Alternate Hydro Energy Center (India), Xi'an Jiaotong University (China people Republic), , King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonbure (Thailand), University of Tokyo (Japan), "MEI" National research at the University (Russian Federation), Russian Academy of Sciences, Siberia Department of Thermal Physics Scientific Research Institute, Uzbekistan "Physics-Sun" IChB of the Academy of Sciences (Republic of Uzbekistan kasi), at the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction (Republic of Uzbekistan si) and the Fergana Polytechnic Institute (Uzbekistan). in microcosms is being conducted.

The world in practice sunny heating systems design and helium of devices improved constructions count and hydrodynamic and thermal processes carried out in them acceleration methods have been developed. Solar cuv heaters efficiency increase features learning one row scientists, especially Dj.A. Duffy, U.A. Beckman, S.A. Klein, G.O. Loff, H.S. Hottel, Dj. Considered in the works of Twydell, A. Weir and others. In these works structural and mode parameters of solar water heater devices optimization and efficiency dependence studied. S.I. Smirnov, O.S. Popel, S.E. Fried, V.I. Vissarionov, V.A. Butuzov, M.D. Rabinovich, A.R. Firth, N.W. Kharchenko, B.M. Khrustalev, V.V. Kuvshinov, R.A. Zakhidov, R.R. Avezov, Yu.K. Rashidov, A.I. Ismanjanov, Sh.I. Klychev, G.N. Uzakov, N.R. It was studied in the work of Avezova et al. With that It should

also be mentioned that the efficient use of solar collectors the structure of the heat supply systems in which they are installed, flow in them to the thermal and hydrodynamic processes that take place and to the operating parameters connection being yes not fully explored and not optimized.

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